

A study to assess effectiveness of planned teaching programme on knowledge regarding water born diseases among mothers of under five children in selected area of selected city

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ABSTRACT

Background: Water borne diseases are the most emerging and re-emerging infectious diseases causing morbidity and mortality among underfiveage group children throughout the world. Mothers knowledge about water borne diseases and it's prevention depends upon various factors such as age of the mother, religion, educational background, occupation, number of children, family income per month, type of family, source of drinking water, type of excreta disposal, type of drainage system, source of information.

Materials and methods: The design adopted for the present study is In present study, a Quasi experimental research design is adopted. Total number of among mothers of under five children 100 sample size respectively. In this study Non-probability purposive sampling technique.

Results: The chi value of age was $\chi=22.431$ with 4 degree of freedom, source of drinking water was $\chi=16.685$ with 4 degree of freedom and toilet facility was $\chi=10.907$

Conclusion: The present study shows that most of the mothers were not having adequate knowledge on prevention of selected water borne diseases. The knowledge were strong positively correlated. There is a need to educate the mothers about water borne diseases and its prevention. This Study assess the effectiveness of planned teaching programme on knowledge regarding water born diseases among mothers of under five children according to findings there was a increased level of knowledge after planned teaching programme

INTRODUCTION

The Waterborne diseases most commonly are transmitted in contaminated fresh water. Infection commonly results during bathing, washing, drinking, in the preparation of food, or the consumption of food thus infected. Various forms of waterborne diarrheal disease probably are the most prominent examples, and affect mainly children in developing countries; according to the World Health Organization, such diseases account for an estimated 4.1% of the total daily global burden of disease, and cause about 1.8 million human deaths annually.

The World Health Organization estimates that 88% of that burden is attributable to unsafe water supply, sanitation and hygiene Microorganism causing diseases that characteristically are waterborne prominently include protozoa and bacteria many of which are intestinal parasites, or invade the tissues or circulatory system through walls of the digestive tract. Various other waterborne diseases are caused by viruses. (In spite of philosophical difficulties associated with defining viruses as "organisms", it is practical and convenient to regard them as microorganisms in this connection) Yet other important classes of water- borne diseases are caused by metazoan parasites. Typical examples include certain Nematodes, that is to say "roundworms".

As an example of water-borne Nematode infections, one important waterborne nematode disease is Dracunculiasis. It is acquired by swallowing water in which certain copepod occur that act as vectors for the worm disease. Water borne diseases are among one of the major public health problems in developing countries like Ethiopia. They are the leading causes of morbidity and mortality in all age ps particularly in children under 5 years of age. According to the World the Organization (WHO) 3 million deaths occur every year from diarrheal password wide.

The problem of water borne diseases is especially prevalent where general hygiene and 2

environmental sanitation are poor and where there is a shortage of protected water supply (1, 5). It is believed that 80% of all diseases in the world are caused by inadequate sanitation, polluted water or unavailability of water (WHO Monica II). Poverty, illiteracy, overcrowding and low health services are contributing factors that directly or indirectly affect the prevalence of water borne diseases.

Therefore an integrated prevention and curative approach with community participation is required in order to tackle this prevalent public health problem. Water borne diseases are viral, bacterial and parasitic diseases which use water as a common means of transmission. The causative agents of water borne diseases are broadly categorized as bacterial, viral, protozoa and helminthes. There is abundant evidence that improving only water quality or only latrines will have little or no effect on the incidence of water borne diseases. Thus there has to be a holistic intervention approach to these problems.

The prevention and control measures include: ¾ Sanitary disposal of human waste. ¾ Protecting public water supplies from fecal contamination. ¾ Treatment of suspected water supplies, both rural and urban, before consumption. ¾ Keeping fetched water at home safe during storage. ¾ Treatment of known carriers. ¾ Mass treatment during epidemic outbreaks, e.g. at schools, in prisons etc. ¾ Treatment of surface water supplies. Washing hands with soap and water before preparing or eating food and after using the latrine. ¾ Health Education. Latrine. ¾ Health Education.1

Each year, waterborne diseases afflict hundreds of millions of people, primarily those living without safe, accessible water in developing countries. Of the seven most common waterborne diseases in the world, diarrhea is the central symptom. The latest research shows that diarrhea is the second leading cause of death for children under the age of five, causing more childhood deaths than malaria, AIDS, and measles combined. That's hundreds of thousands of deaths, but there is hope for the future.

Experts believe we can end the global water and sanitation crisis in our lifetime. Waterborne diseases are illnesses caused by microscopic organisms, like viruses and bacteria, that are ingested through contaminated water or by coming in contact with feces. If every person on the planet was able to practice safe sanitation and hygiene and have access to clean water, these diseases would not exist. Governments, NGOs, and communities themselves have 3

made great strides in the past 20 years to end waterborne diseases. Still, there is much to be done.2

Clean water is the single most important resource that all societies are entitled to. Our lives revolve around water – from drinking to cooking to bathing. But millions of people, especially in poor and developing countries don't have access to safe drinking water. Poor sanitation and unhygienic conditions breed micro-organisms that spread waterborne diseases, causing breakouts of diseases that have the ability to affect a whole community. Diseases by water can affect us anytime, anywhere. Therefore it's

important to be vigilant, keep our environment clean, and practice good hygiene at all times. Some of the most common water borne diseases in India are: Malaria, Typhoid, Cholera, Giardiasis, Amoebic Dysentery, Amoebiasis, Hepatitis A, Shigellosis During COVID-19, we understand that seeking help and getting appropriate treatment for water borne diseases may be hard.

They are diseases that are transmitted by ingesting contaminated water, food and contact with faces that contain harmful bacteria, viruses and other disease causing-microorganisms. Important: "Water related disease is transmitted through water which is contaminated and if you ingest water from unclean sources such as public tanks, lakes or tap water (which is often contaminated in India), From Gastroenteritis to typhoid and amoebiasis, there are a number of health conditions that can occur due to consumption of contaminated water."

There are two major causes of water related diseases :(i) Waterborne pathogens such as viruses and bacteria that are ingested through contaminated water(ii) Contact with waste products such as faces through contaminated water.

Industrial areas in India often have contaminated waterbodies because the waste from factories contains toxic materials that are dumped into nearby lakes and rivers. According to the United Nations, over 1 lakh Indians die due to disease from water contamination every year. Around 37.7 million Indians are affected by consuming contaminated water every year, ranging from simple diarrhea to more complicated infections. This is mainly due to lack of access to safe drinking water and living in unsanitary conditions. Rivers such as the Ganges provide water for nearly 500 million people in India. So contamination of even one water source can affect a large part of the population. 4

It is important to make sure you boil water before drinking or using it for cooking purposes to protect yourself from water borne diseases. Most of these diseases can be treated at an early stage. The first step to preventing serious complications from diseases from water is to ensure you stay hydrated. Treatment of these diseases mainly includes rehydration, rest, and sometimes medication and antibiotics. Water borne diseases are extremely common in India and anybody can fall prey to them. Therefore, understanding the nature of these diseases and being able to identify the symptoms in time is crucial for their treatment.

The second wave of COVID in India is raging, with thousands of people succumbing to the deadly disease every day. (Conjunctivitis Abdominal pain Diarrhea) Research has revealed that the novel coronavirus is airborne which means when a person, coughs, sneezes or talks, droplets containing the virus are released and can stay in the air for up to 3 hours. Any person within 6ft of the transmitter can get infected. There is another study reveals that the novel coronavirus can be transmitted through contaminated water. They can survive for 10 days in contaminated tap water and coming in contact with the water will infect you easily. While there are different kinds of diseases that stem from contaminated water, there are a few

which are extremely common in India and there is no collective, common disease symptoms. These diseases typically occur both in rural and urban areas, so it's important to take strict precautions no matter where you live. Here are the characteristics and symptoms of 8 most common water borne diseases in India:

Typhoid: Typhoid is a common bacterial waterborne disease caused by the *Salmonella typhi* bacteria. This disease is often seen in places where personal hygiene is low and hand washing is not practiced enough. According to one report, around 494 out of every 1,00,000 children in India suffer from typhoid. A lot of villages and smaller towns in India with poor sanitation face a higher risk of typhoid. However, it can also occur in urban cities during the monsoons and it is during this period that the symptoms of typhoid become noticeable.

Cholera: Second in the water borne diseases list is Cholera, a water related disease caused by the bacterium *Vibrio cholera*. It is commonly transmitted through contaminated food and faces. According to a report by WHO, there are around 4 million cases of cholera each year. India has experienced cholera outbreaks in the past and there are still active cases of cholera in the country. One study of an at-risk locality in Kolkata found that there were around 2.2 5

cases out of every 1000 people. It's extremely important that we maintain good hygiene and sanitation to contain the spread of cholera and protect ourselves from it.

Malaria: Malaria fever is caused by plasmodium parasites and is transmitted by the female *Anopheles* mosquito that breeds on stagnant, unclean water such as lakes and sewage drains. When a carrier mosquito bites you, the parasite enters your bloodstream and goes straight to the liver, the site of RBC production. There, the parasite attacks your RBCs and infected RBCs burst open, resulting in malaria symptoms and the onset of the disease. According to the WHO, India reports around 15 million cases of malaria each year. Sewage systems and public water bodies, if maintained well will significantly reduce Malaria cases.

Giardiasis: is a parasitic infection caused by *Giardia lamblia*, a water-based pathogen, that mainly spreads through a face-oral contamination route and affects the small intestine. May have contact *Giardia* by eating contaminated food or drinking contaminated water. It is quite common in India and countries with cramped spaces and poor sanitation in communities. *Giardia lamblia* is most commonly found in human and animal faces. Swimming pools, lakes and public water bodies are the most common infection points of this water related disease. It mostly spreads when people come into contact with infected faces

Amoebic Dysentery: Amoebic dysentery is a water borne disease that mainly spreads through contaminated food, water and contact with faecal matter. It is an intestinal infection which leads to inflammation as well as severe abdominal cramps and diarrhea. Blood and mucous in the stools is common too.

Amoebic dysentery usually lasts for 3-7 days.

Hepatitis A: Viruses which cause Hepatitis are transmitted through contaminated water. Hepatitis A is a sub-type of the hepatitis virus that occurs by exposure to contaminated food and water. Hepatitis A infection leads to the inflammation of the liver and temporarily affects liver function. Fortunately, Hepatitis A is not very serious or fatal and generally goes away on its own in a few days. However, if symptoms persist your doctor will recommend medications and antibiotics to combat the disease. 6

Shigellosis: Shigellosis is caused by the Shigella bacteria and it affects the intestine, resulting in diarrhea and vomiting. It is a common disease that spreads through the faeco-oral route. Sheila bacteria is present in contaminated water, food and faces. Shigellosis commonly occurs in toddlers and school-going children, because they tend to touch dirty surfaces and put their fingers in their mouths.

Amoebiasis: Amoebiasis is caused by the protozoan Entamoebahistolytica. It affects the intestines and causes loose stools, water loss and stomach cramps. It usually goes away on its own with rest and rehydration. Amoebiasis is waterborne and enters the body through contaminated food, drinks and faces. When you ingest small cysts containing E.Histolytica, you will get infected. If infected, a person can spread the disease through fecal contamination.

Mothers are the key caregivers for children under five years old. They are the one who can decide about the prevention of water borne diseases in children therefore their knowledge about this common disorder is critically important. Hence there is a need to undertake a study to assess the knowledge and practices of mothers of fewer than five children on prevention of selected water borne diseases.3

The children consist about 20% of our total population are prone to get infections from different sources like food, water, flies, fomites and polluted environment. All aspects of child care are looked after by the mother only. So mother have prime role in the prevention of water borne diseases. Waterborne diseases represent a major burden on human health worldwide. Every year, 1.8 million people die from diarrheal diseases, of which 1.5 million are children under the age of 5. Access to safe drinking water, basic sanitation and proper hygiene education could not only prevent diarrheal diseases by nearly 90% but furthermore lead to improved health, poverty reduction and socioeconomic development. Goal 7 of the Millennium Development goals (MDG) set by the United Nations in 2000 is to halve by 2015 the proportion of people without sustainable access to safe drinking water and basic sanitation.

Problem Statement

“A study to assess effectiveness of planned teaching programme on knowledge regarding water born diseases among mothers of under five children in selected area of selected city”.

Objectives of the Study

1. To assess the pre-existing knowledge regarding the water borne diseases.
2. To assess the post-test knowledge regarding the water bornediseases
3. To compare pre-test post -test knowledge regarding the water borne diseases
4. To assess the association between level of knowledge regarding the water borne diseases and selected socio-demographic variables.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials and methods: The design adopted for the present study is In present study, a Quasi experimental research design is adopted. Total number of among mothers of under five children 100 sample size respectively. In this study Non-probability purposive sampling technique.

Hypotheses

H01: There is significant difference in knowledge, among mother of under five children after implementation of planned teaching program.

H1: There is no significant difference in knowledge, among mother of under five children after implementation of planned teaching program.

H02 : There is no significant association between knowledge, among mother of under five children after implementation of planned teaching program with their selected socio-demographic variables.

H2 : There is significant association between knowledge, among mother of under five children after implementation of planned teaching program with their selected socio-demographic variables.

RESULTS:**Section I: Frequency distribution of socio demographic variables among mothers of under five children****Table 1- Frequency and percentage distribution of by age**

N=100 Sr. No	Age of the mother	Frequency	Percentage
1	19-22	24	24.00
	23-25	34	34.00
	26-30	17	17.00
	31-35	25	25.00

Section II: Assessment of pre-test level of knowledge regarding water borne diseases among mothers.**Table 12- Frequency and percentage distribution of pre-test level of knowledge regarding water borne diseases among mothers.**

N=100 Level of Knowledge	Score	Frequency	Percentage
Poor knowledge	0-7	44	44
Average knowledge	8-14	46	46
Good knowledge	15-20	10	10

Section III: Evaluate the effectiveness of planned teaching program between pretest& post level of knowledge on water borne diseases among mother of under five children.

Table -14 Effectiveness of planned health teaching on knowledge on knowledge of water borne diseases among mother of under five children.

N=100 Test	Mean	SD	SEM	T	DF	P-value
Pre-test	7.40	3.58	0.36	13.884	99	p<0.0001
Post-test		13.50		2.58		0.26

Section IV: Association between knowledge scores and selected demographic variables of mother of under five children.

Table no 15: Association between pretest knowledge score and demograph ic variables Sr. NO	Demograp hic Variables	Level of knowledge	df	Chi square Value	P Value	Significanc e
1		Average				
				Age of mother		
19-22	7	16	1	6	6.853	0.335
23-25		18		13		3
26-30		7		7		3
31-35		12		10		3
2				Type of family		
Nuclear	29	27	3	2	4.347	0.114
Joint family		15		19		7
Extended family		0		0		0
3				Mother's education		
Graduate or post graduate	21	13	3	6	5.376	0.497
Intermediate or post high school		3		5		1
High school certificate		5		10		3
No formal education		15		18		3
4				Mother's occupation		
Semi profession	2	1	1		2.156	976
Clerical , shop, farmer	10		10		3	8
Semi skilled worker		3		4		1
Unskilled worker		10		11		2
House wife		19		20		3

5		Father's education					
Graduate or post graduate	21	13	3	6	5.376	0.497	Not significant
Intermediate or post high school		3		5		1	
High school certificate		5		10		3	
No formal education		15		18		3	
6		Source of drinking water					
Well	11	8	3	6	11.247	0.08	Not significant
Tap water		11		24		2	
Bore water		16		9		5	
Other		6		5		0	
7		Locality					
Urban	21	24	5	4	0.435	0.980	Not significant
Rural		12		13		3	

DISCUSSION

-An analysis of the data has helped the investigator to get clear understanding of the study undertaken. The interpretation drawn from the findings of the study were based on objectives of the study.

The study was found that Majority among mothers of under five children graduated or post graduated group wear 37 % involved ,followed to ,High school certificate 18% , Intermediate high school 9% No formal education 36% respectively. Majority were found fathers of under five children wear 37% graduated & majority no formal education 36% wear seen, & 18 % in high school certificate,& Intermediate high-school wear 9% respectively. Majority were found 37% tap water, wear 30% bore water 22% well water & 11 % other sources of drinking water respectively.

1.The first objective of the study was to assess the pre-existing knowledge regarding the water borne diseases .It is found that Majority of level of pre-test knowledge found good level of knowledge wear 10%, Average level of knowledge 46% ,poor level knowledge 44 % respectively.

2.Second objective of the study was to assess post-test knowledge regarding the water borne diseases ,as according to findings , majority of level of post-test knowledge were found poor knowledge wear 2% , average level of knowledge 61% ,good knowledge 37% respectively.

3.Third objective of the study is to compare pre-test & post -test knowledge regarding the water borne diseases, as according to findings there was a significant difference between pre –test (7.4) and post -test of knowledge (13.5) t-value, $P < 0.0001$ respectively research hypothesis(H1) is accepted ($p < 0.0001$) respectively.

4.Fourth objective of the study is to assess the association between level of knowledge regarding the water borne diseases and selected socio- demographic variables. As according to findings it reveals that in pre-test there was no significant association between, age ,type of family ,mothers education ,mothers occupation, fathers education ,source of drinking water locality ,type of diagnosis, need for mechanical ventilation, child exposure to passive smoking null hypothesis(H02) is accepted respectively.

5.In order to compute the association between the level of knowledge score and demographic variables chi-square was applied and the value was observed with 5% significance level, The chi value of toilet facility was $\chi^2 = 16.206$ with 4 degree of freedom was found association with level of knowledge score

6. Findings reveals that in post –test there was no significant association between, type of family ,mothers education ,mothers occupation, fathers education, locality ,type of diagnosis, need for mechanical ventilation, child exposure to passive smoking null hypothesis(H02) is accepted respectively. The Chi-square was applied and the value was observed with 5% significance level, The chi value of age was $\chi=22.431$ with 4 degree of freedom, source of drinking water was $\chi=16.685$ with 4 degree of freedom and toilet facility was $\chi=10.907$ with 4 degree of freedom was found association with level of knowledge score hypothesis(H01)) is accepted respectively.

Varalakshmi.E, MahalakshmiR ,PrashanthKet,al (2020). A Study to Assess the Knowledge and Practice on Water Borne Diseases and its Prevention Mothers of Under Five Children. We found that Infection commonly results during bathing, washing, drinking, in the preparation of food, or the consumption of food thus infected. The Major findings of the study were overall mean score is 26.83 with a mean percentage 89.43% and standard deviation 2.93. A significant relationship was observed between education, food pattern and source of information with the knowledge. Whereas age, occupation, monthly income and type of family do not show any relationship of mothers regarding water borne diseases and its prevention. Result of this study reveals that 8.33% of mothers were having moderate knowledge of water borne diseases and its prevention and 91.67% of mothers were having adequate knowledge on water borne diseases and its prevention.4

LathaP, RenukaK, Karthi R and SrinivasanN ,et,al(2020) Conducted a study on Knowledge regarding prevention of water borne disease among mothers of under five children at Nellipaka village, Bhadrachalam, Telangana. water borne diseases among mother of under five children. A quantitative approach with descriptive design, 50 mothers of under five children were selected by using simple random sampling technique. Study revealed that, among 50 mothers of under five children, 22(44%) had inadequate knowledge, 3(6%) have moderate knowledge and 25(50%) had adequate knowledge regarding water borne diseases and its prevention.44 67

CONCLUSION:

The present study shows that most of the mothers were not having adequate knowledge on prevention of selected water borne diseases. The knowledge were strong positively correlated. There is a need to educate the mothers about water borne diseases and its prevention. This Study assess the effectiveness of planned teaching programme on knowledge regarding water born diseases among mothers of under five children according to findings there was a increased level of knowledge after planned teaching programme

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